

Exploring Support Available For Teachers In Implementing Annual Teaching Plan At Secondary Schools In King Cetshwayo District

Gladys Phumzile Mngomezulu, Kofi Nkonkonya Mpuangnan,
Samantha Govender

Teacher support contributes to create a positive and conducive environment for teaching and learning which benefits learners' academic achievement, promoting teachers' professional growth and overall well-being of both learners and teachers. This qualitative study delves into exploring the kind of support available to teachers in the implementation of Annual Teaching Plan at secondary schools in King Cetshwayo district, South Africa. The focus of this article is to establish the kind of support available to teachers in the implementation of the Annual Teaching Plan for quality teaching and learning. The aim is to explore teachers' perspectives on professional development provided for establishing the Annual Teaching Plan for curriculum coverage. To achieve this, the research adopted a qualitative methodology, employing a case study design. Data collection involved a combination of semi-structured interviews conducted through both focus group discussions and one-on-one sessions with 18 teachers and 6 Heads of Departments responsible for the Further Education Training Phase. The participants were selected purposively from six secondary schools situated in King Cetshwayo District. The study's findings revealed that teachers receive minimal professional development to assist them apply the pace setters for curriculum coverage. The findings also demonstrated that the support provided by the Department was relevant yet insufficient, and often came too late. In light of these issues, it is suggested that the Department of Basic Education should offer regular, adequate and relevant continuous professional development to capacitate teachers with comprehensive knowledge and innovative approaches linking theory and practice and have enough time to apply knowledge gained. This continuous professional development would allow teachers to refine their skills and adapt their practices to increase both teaching and curriculum coverage.

Key words: *Teacher Support Mechanisms; Professional Development; Curriculum Coverage; Quality Teaching And Learning; Innovative Approaches; Pace Setting*

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Introduction

Teacher support in education is crucial for academic development and the provision of quality education for a country. The support equips teachers with necessary skills and approaches to provide guidance and expertise to learners helping them to understand complex concepts, develop critical thinking and master academic content. The support encompasses forms of assistance, resources, and professional development opportunities provided to teachers to enhance their effectiveness in the classroom. African education has consistently embarked on various initiatives with the primary goal of improving the quality of education and preparing students to excel in the global economy. One such initiative is the Curriculum and Assessment Policy Statement (CAPS), orchestrated by the Department of Education. CAPS curriculum, through Annual Teaching Plans (ATP), prescribes specific timeframes within which teachers are expected to cover the curriculum.

- i. What support is available for teachers in the implementation of Annual Teaching Plan (ATP) for quality teaching and learning?

- ii. What are teachers' perspectives for support provided in implementing Annual Teaching Plan at secondary schools in King Cetshwayo district

Literature Review

1. Support mechanisms available for teachers

The provision of adequate support mechanisms for teachers emerges as a global concern, particularly in developing nations (Mdikana, 2022; Osai et al. 2021; Subekti, 2021). Numerous studies have delved into the support teachers receive to enhance their effectiveness in delivering quality education, shedding light on the challenges they encounter in aligning their teaching practices with the curriculum expectations set by educational authorities (Wambugu, Stutchebury & Dickie, 2019; Govender, 2018; Nkambule, 2018; Ajani, 2019). While education systems worldwide aspire to offer learners high-quality learning experiences, foster a culture of lifelong learning, and cultivate productive citizenship, teachers often perceive a lack of sustainable professional development programs and minimal opportunities for meaningful classroom support, guidance, and supervision to aid in implementing necessary changes and boosting effective learning (Govender, 2018; Nkambule, 2018; Subekti, 2021).

The rapid pace of curriculum changes has led to a situation where many teachers find themselves lacking necessary knowledge, as their initial training did not encompass the new curriculum requirements. Therefore, scholars such as Ulla and Winitkun (2018), Ajani (2019), and Du Plessis (2019) advocate for the implementation of continuous professional development at regular intervals to enhance effective teaching and learning and uphold the integrity of the education system. This necessitates that the Department of Education takes responsibility for organizing workshops aimed at in-service professional development, ensuring that teachers receive adequate support to adapt their teaching methodologies to align with new educational policies in schools. In-service professional development initiatives equip teachers with innovative approaches to delivering content, refining teaching strategies, engaging with new educational materials, and sustaining a high standard of ongoing education, all of which are vital for effective classroom instruction (Ulla & Winitkun, 2018; Ajani, 2019; Chitiyo et al., 2019).

In Senegal and Nigeria, the cluster system has emerged as a notable professional development strategy, serving as a crucial tool in enhancing teachers' competencies and ensuring the delivery of high-quality education (Diop, 2021; Ajani & Govender, 2018). Researchers highlighted that this system enables teachers to collaborate effectively by exchanging ideas, skills, and knowledge, thereby fostering continuous improvement in their teaching practices and offering regular avenues for personal development. Additionally, teachers have the chance to engage in mutual observation, reflective practices, and providing constructive feedback, all of which contribute to the refinement of their teaching methods.

Kenya introduced a school-based professional development strategy involving classroom observations as part of a program implementation (Wambugu, Stutchbury, & Dickie in 2019). These observations served as a valuable tool for fostering dynamic learning methods among teachers, demonstrating techniques for integrating collaboration and teamwork into lessons, utilizing local resources for teaching materials, and customizing activities to fit specific teaching environments. Additionally, teachers participated in discussions and self-reflection sessions. The results highlighted the effectiveness of this approach, indicating that through collaborative efforts, teachers successfully addressed challenges and cultivated positive interactions with students in the classroom.

Canadian teachers are actively involved in a variety of professional development activities, including workshops, seminars or educational conferences, networking with other teachers, and individual or collaborative research and in-service training (Campbell, 2017). Workshops and collaborative learning are predominant at the provincial level, and the curriculum is developed and monitored by the provinces, rather than by the national government. Collaborative learning takes place among classrooms, schools, districts and educational professionals. According to Campbell (2017), teachers in Canada spend an average of one to three hours a week on professional learning, and teachers meet with district facilitators seven times a year to explore challenges and answer questions. This approach offers a wide variety of opportunities for teachers to have their concerns addressed and to receive the help they need to meet their specific circumstances.

At the school level, the overall management of the curriculum is the responsibility of the School Management Team (SMT) which includes the HODs, the deputy principal (DP) and the principal of the school. The HODs are required to perform curriculum leadership roles such as monitoring, moderating, developing, managing, administering, providing instructional support and ensuring positive learner and teacher performance in schools (Terhoven & Fataar, 2018; Tapala, Fuller & Kobus, 2020). This means that the SMT needs to implement a range of collaborative practices to ensure that activities to do with curriculum implementation are effectively managed. Their support goes a long way to improving quality education in schools.

However, HODs in Northwest Province, South Africa, reiterated that the unmanageable workload caused barriers to fulfil their responsibilities. Twelve HODs who participated in a qualitative study by Tapala, Van Niekerk and Mentz (2021) indicated that HODs lack the time to perform certain duties, lack training and professional development, communicated poorly amongst each other, and struggled with changes in the curriculum. These barriers had a negative effect on the way in which the HODs executed their roles. They were aware that teachers' implementation of the curriculum rested on them. The study recommended well-designed training and development specifically for HODs, which would have a cascading effect on all teachers.

Therefore, curriculum implementation requires continuous professional teacher development and support, so that teachers can actually contribute towards quality teaching and learning. South Africa's Department of Basic Education is attempting to create education that equips learners with necessary knowledge and skills to uplift the country's economy (Malik, 2018) and adapt to the changing world (Schulz, Ainley, Frallion, Losito & Agrust, 2018). Given the challenges of the curriculum as discussed above, the Department is obligated to create support mechanisms to assist teachers to cover all content at the required level. Support or the lack of it is a major issue and has implications for the quality of teaching and learning that takes place.

2. Teachers' perspectives for support provided in implementing Annual Teaching Plan at secondary schools

The insufficient training of teachers stands out as a key challenge impeding the successful execution of the curriculum in educational institutions (Pak, Polikoff, Desimone & Saldívar, 2020). Umugiraneza, Bansilal and North (2018) conducted a study investigating teachers' ways of working with the curriculum in the teaching of statistics in Mathematics in KwaZulu-Natal schools. Data obtained through questionnaires from 75 Mathematics teachers who had attended an in-service training programme revealed that their poor training had created a major gap between the knowledge they possessed and the knowledge they needed to teach the new curriculum. The study found that teachers lacked an understanding of how to integrate curriculum changes into their teaching of Mathematics. It concluded that teachers need a great deal more training to become proficient in the new curriculum (Gul, Tahir & Ishfaq, 2023; Baikenov, 2020).

Govender (2018) conducted a qualitative study with 20 Language and Mathematics teachers, based on in-depth interviews. The aim of the study was to explore the challenges teachers face in implementing curriculum changes, and the support they receive from the Department of Basic Education in uThungulu District, KwaZulu-Natal. The findings indicated dissatisfaction from the participants. The teachers felt that the support they received was not enough, and that they had limited opportunities to receive meaningful guidance and monitoring to assist them. This study suggested that raising the level of support and expanding internal capacity could strengthen the base of overall support available to teachers and would enable better teaching and learning. The challenge, of course, is finding the time for in-service training. Teachers should not be trained during school hours, which means that any training conducted has to take place at weekends or during school holidays.

Another study on the experiences of secondary school Social Science teachers in Limpopo found that the time available for in-service training workshops was not enough, and that these workshops were not achieving policy expectations (Maepa, 2017; Damianidou, 2024). Nkambule and Amsterdam (2018) explored the support available to teachers and found that it was inadequate, leaving many teachers feeling ill equipped to face the challenges of the educational policy. Thus, the literature suggests that inadequate initial training in combination with inadequate in-service training contributes to the poor implementation of education policies. Moreover, Mbatha's (2016) study on teachers' experiences of implementing the CAPS curriculum in secondary schools at Ndwedwe near Durban discovered that teachers needed the assistance of principals, heads of department, subject advisors and the Department of Basic Education in order to cope with effective implementation of education policies and substantial curriculum reform.

Similarly, a study referred to earlier by Booysen (2018) in Northwest Province found that teachers do not receive adequate in-service training to adapt teaching strategies and assessment in line with the curriculum changes and are unable to meet the needs of all learners.

In Thailand, Ulla and Winitkun (2018) examined the challenges teachers face with in-service training programmes. At the time of the study, Thailand had recently updated their education system to improve learners' poor English performance, which was linked to poor teaching strategies. In-service training programmes were strengthened to equip teachers with the necessary knowledge, skills and methodology to teach, with a particular focus on teachers who had been in service for many years.

In Zimbabwe, Ndoziya (2014) found that SMT members tended to concentrate on their managerial role and spent a great deal of time attending meetings with departmental officials. As a result, teachers lacked the support they needed which could have contributed to their growth and development. Chabalala (2020) argues that teachers need support from the SMT to capacitate them to deliver the curriculum as expected, and to ensure improvements in learners' results. Despite widespread desire to implement the curriculum properly, the support teachers receive from both the SMTs and the Department of Basic Education remains a challenge, especially in secondary schools.

Unfortunately, even novice teachers who are most in need of practical support suffer from too little contact with and support from the SMT (Nkambule & Amsterdam, 2018). According to Shava, Maradze and Ncube (2021), the SMT's responsibility is to improve the quality of teaching and learning effectively and efficiently. However, a qualitative study by Ntsoane's (2017) examined the role of SMT members in the induction of novice teachers in rural schools, revealing that novice teachers encountered a range of challenges when entering the profession. Data collected from novice teachers in six rural schools in Limpopo Province showed that novice teachers received too little assistance from the SMT, meetings were infrequent and poorly conducted, and that any orientation and mentoring that did take place was haphazard and informal. Benoliel (2017) argued that the SMT needs to manage its roles and functioning well and provide the professional leadership required to build a positive learning environment. Benoliel's (2017) findings also show that SMT members do not have the training to induct novice teachers properly, which

adversely affects both their role and the experience of the novice teachers. The study recommended additional support and training for SMT members, as well as improved laws and policies regarding guidance for novices.

SMTs often overlook the need for professional development in the school. Botha (2019) conducted a study exploring how SMT members managed the professional development of teachers at schools in the Ekurhuleni District, Gauteng. Data obtained from semi-structured interviews with 15 purposefully sampled participants in five secondary schools showed that there was a lack of formal professional development in schools. This was due to several factors, including lack of understanding of the concept of professional development, lack of clear guidelines for professional development, lack of resources needed to carry out professional development, and improper management of the professional development process. Therefore, Botha's (2019) study recommends that all stakeholders work together to compile specific SMT policies and practices that will assist, encourage and support teachers' professional development in schools. These guidelines would ensure that teachers' education and development is carried out regularly to enhance the knowledge of teachers and to ensure that their qualifications and expertise are valued.

The reviewed literature thus provides insight into the state of pace setting in South Africa and elsewhere, along with the challenges teachers experience and the support mechanisms available to help them. The number of studies on support available to teachers specifically to cover the curriculum at the required pace is limited. Clearly pace is an issue in most countries, but especially in developing countries where curricula have been designed for more ideal circumstances than prevail on the ground. As a result of the challenges that teachers encounter, they clearly need a great deal of support through in-service training which should be well planned, responsive to real situations and offered more frequently.

Methodology

The study used a qualitative methodology to gather secondary school teachers' perspectives on how ATP affect curriculum coverage and the standard of instruction. This research provided an opportunity to learn about the viewpoints and beliefs of the subjects (Creswell, 2014; Palikans, Horwitz, Green, Wisdom & Duan, 2015).

Participants

18 teachers and 6 Heads of Departments from secondary schools in the King Cetshwayo district were chosen as study participants. Purposive sampling was used to choose the participants in addition to random selection of the schools. The selection process was based on the candidate's expertise and years of experience instructing English at the Further Education and Training (FET) phase. As a result, codes such as T1, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, T8, T9, T10, T11, T12, T13, T14, T15, T16, T17, and T18 for teachers were assigned to the chosen participants. Also, the Heads of departments (HOD) were assigned a unique code HOD1, HOD2, HOD3, HOD4, HOD5, HOD6. The participants' information was gathered using a semi-structured interview schedule.

The purpose of the interview questions was to find out what the teachers thought about the ways in which the ATP technique impacts curriculum coverage, teaching quality, and academic performance of students. Three education experts checked the questions for grammar and content accuracy to ensure they were clear and effective. After receiving their input, the questions were improved and used in participant interviews.

Data analysis

Teachers' opinions on how the pace-setter strategy impacts curriculum coverage, teaching quality, and students' academic success were the main emphasis of the interview questions. Three education experts checked the questions for grammatical errors and content accuracy to ensure they were clear and effective. The questions were improved in response to their input before being utilized in participant interviews.

Findings And Discussions

Findings were presented and discussed following themes emerged from the analysis of the transcripts. With secondary school teachers and Heads of the Departments. The schools were in rural, semi-rural and urban areas of King Cetshwayo district, South Africa. The participants were teachers and Heads of Departments in the FET phase, grade 10 to 12.

Support mechanisms available for teachers

Workshops are identified as a key component of support system teachers receive in secondary schools which focus on familiarizing teachers with the use of the ATPs to ensure consistency in their teaching practice. However, teachers have different perspectives regarding the kind of support mechanisms available for them to implement pace setters for curriculum coverage. Responses showed that even though the support is available, but it does not equip them with the skills of keeping up with the prescribed pace whilst providing quality teaching and learning in classroom practice. Participant T13 mentioned that workshops are organized to monitor the usage of ATP to ensure adherence to the guidelines: *"The Department set up a series of workshops that deals with the usage of the ATP. The school as well is urged and monitored on the usage of the ATP. The ATP is used as a tool to search and check if the teaching and learning is actually occurring in schools"*.

By so doing the department ensures a standardized approach to education across different schools and that schools are not only following the ATP but also achieve intended educational outcomes aligned with prescribed standards and goals. Professional development for teachers must be ongoing in order to make sure that teaching methods are modified to comply with the new education policies and to guarantee quality teaching and learning. The participants further expressed that through collaboration on WhatsApp group they are able to share knowledge and solve problems: *“Subject advisors are always there to guide us; we’ve got What’s App groups where we easily access our subject advisors. She is easily contacted when you have problems. We have access to a Science Centre which works hand in hand with Unizulu. We also have workshops, and even the SMT provides us with every support we need. The Department provided us with revision booklets which contain previous question papers.”* T18.

Participant T8 concurred, indicating that not much professional support was provided hence they received support system which is in the form of a structured approach which maintain managing of files and verifying learners’ work to ensure that teachers are aligned with the ATPs. This approach illustrate commitment to accountability, consistency and monitoring to achieve educational objectives which in this case is the curriculum coverage: *“We do get support from our departmental heads; they manage our files to see whether we are in line with the ATPs. They also check learners’ work to verify whether it is in line with the ATPs. In terms of the Department, we do have our subject advisors who conduct workshops. For instance, in term one we used to have the workshop in the second week, where we are orientated with all these documents for moderation, assessment and teaching in a particular subject.”* T8. Govender and Ajani (2021) perceived that monitoring teacher's files is administrative rather than aiding professional development. Moreover, studies from Cebu indicated that teachers’ professional development play a critical role in teacher performance (Kilag et al, 2023). Kelly, Mckenzie, Watermeyer, Vergunst, Karisa, & Samuels (2024) emphasize that inadequate support available for teachers leave many teachers feeling ill equipped to face the new developments in the education system and engage with new materials

Participant T14 mentioned that the department has organized a series of workshops not only to encourage but also to monitor the usage of ATP to ensure adherence to the guidelines. Therefore, the use of the ATP in this capacity underscores its importance in maintaining educational quality and accountability. By so doing the department ensures a standardized approach to education across different schools and that schools are not only following the ATP but also achieve intended educational outcomes aligned with prescribed standards and goals: *“The Department set up a series of workshops that deals with the usage of the ATP. The school as well is urged and monitored on the usage of the ATP. The ATP is used as a tool to search and check if the teaching and learning is actually occurring in schools.”* T5.

However, the department heads demonstrated a strong dedication to teamwork and ongoing improvement, which are essential elements of quality teaching and learning. They asserted that by utilizing outside networks, conducting frequent departmental meetings, and offering focused feedback, they promote a culture of professional development. Along with supporting teachers in addressing particular issues, this strategy encourages a shared accountability for the success of learners: *“The thing that I do as a departmental head, I have our departmental meetings. In those meetings, I give feedback to teachers as to where are the shortcomings, and thereafter we have discussions on the way forward. Sometimes we suggest that if the teacher is struggling with a certain topic, we network with other colleagues from other schools. We target those schools with teachers who usually get better results in that subject or [ask] a stronger teacher to come in and assist the teacher with that section. In that way we improve ourselves in terms of professional development. But our school is very equipped in terms of internet. We all have access to internet to download previous exams question papers and anything we want. That is our great advantage; we are able to get a lot of activities to give our learners and do lot of revision.”* HOD4. Collaboration and networking with colleagues who have shown success in particular fields can be very effective for career advancement. This strategy is consistent with the idea of professional learning communities, in which educators collaborate to enhance their practices in a variety of settings (Douglas, 2023; Khasawneh et al. 2023; Vescio, Ross & Adams, 2008). It has been demonstrated that collaborative professional development increases teacher effectiveness and improves student learning outcomes

Teachers’ viewpoints on support provided for establishing the pace setting for curriculum coverage.

The results showed a number of difficulties related to the type of assistance obtained for pace setter implementation to cover curriculum in secondary schools. Pasique and Maguate (2023) assert that workshops are an important tool for professional growth, however participants found that they are not always successful because of timing issues and poor communication: *“Workshops are there, but they are not enough. Sometimes the communication is poor; you find out that there is a workshop very late. They give us question papers and documents at the end of the term and always give excuses why they are late. They talk about shortage of resources such as papers. Workshops are there, but they are not fruitful – they don’t have resources all the time. For example, in term two we received the material at the end of the term when learners were left with three days to write their exams. Maybe if they can make the resources available in terms of soft copies or create a portal to access them.”* T8. This lack of readily available resources and the delayed delivery of necessary materials impair the effectiveness of these workshops and the effective use of resources for learners' progress. Since the availability of resources is a major factor in the success of implementing new strategies learned in workshops, the mention of resource shortages draws attention to the larger problem of

inadequate support for teachers. When these elements are lacking, the ability of teachers to deliver high-quality education is compromised, which directly affects student learning outcomes (Badrinarayan & Darling-Hammond, 2023).

Teachers expressed their dissatisfaction with the Department of Education's lack of adequate and consistent support, especially with regard to professional development workshops and issues that arose after the ATP pace. It was brought up by the participants that they only went to one workshop in the whole year. This suggests that teachers are not receiving enough opportunities for professional development, which leaves them without access to ongoing support or updates on curriculum changes and teaching strategies. Participant T7 highlighted: *"The support that we get from the DoE in the form of workshops are not enough. As we speak, its August already, but we had only one workshop this year, which was conducted at the beginning of the year. They don't do follow-up on challenges we are facing with this ATP pace, whether we are coping or not."* Inference from this suggests that the absence of follow-up support, teachers may find it difficult to meet the demands of the ATP, which could result in inconsistent curriculum delivery and possible gaps in student learning. According to Godwin, Kayoe and Aston (2023) and Nor, Yusuf and Arabi (2024) regular and consistent workshops are essential for upholding new pedagogical approaches and high standards of teaching because teachers risk missing out on important information that could help in improving their methods and addressing issues that arise in the classroom. It is necessary to regularly assess teachers to see if they are keeping up with the ATP's rapid pace, content delivery or learner engagement.

An additional participant recounted their experience from the 2018 workshop and discussed the beneficial effects of such sessions on teaching methods. Since then, though, the lack of workshops has been brought to light, raising serious concerns about the effectiveness of professional development initiatives and the infrastructure put in place to support actual teaching and learning practices. The participant also stated that in order to guarantee noticeable improvements in the classroom, they needed more extensive help to bridge the gap between the ideal outcome and actual classroom practices: *"I went to a workshop in 2018 on how to implement things in the classroom. I can say I received assistance in that workshop. Recently I also went to the 'Trace a concept' workshop in Durban. We were trained on how to improve teaching in schools, but it was not implemented this year. I think maybe they need to improve the number of workshops."* T2. According to Killag et al. (2023), providing frequent professional development can help teachers break up the monotony of their daily work, promote creativity, and help them learn new things.

Participant T2 highlighted a mixed picture of the support systems available to teachers which includes peer collaboration and cluster moderation that provide some level of professional development. This collaboration reinforced the empowerment, developed strong interpersonal relationship amongst teachers, and bridged a gap of professional development. Wullschleger, Voros, Rechsteiner, Rickenbacher and Merki (2023) concur that collaboration is essential for successful improvement processes in schools to respond to discrepancies between expected and actual conditions to improve teaching and learning. The absence of formal guidance and mentorship from subject advisors represents a significant shortfall. The participant admitted of not having met the subject advisor, despite being part of the organisation since 2017, and that bring into light the disconnection between teachers and the advisory structures intended to provide expert support. *"We always have team support whenever there is a difficulty or questions you feel like you are unable to address. I've been here from 2017, but I never met the subject advisor. There was no workshop addressed by the subject advisor. We used to assist each other during moderation in clusters."* T10. This lack of interaction raises concerns about the availability and accessibility of professional development that could serve as a platform for sharing best practices and strategies for overcoming challenges of using pace set for curriculum coverage whilst ensuring the quality teaching and learning in secondary schools. For high quality teaching and learning to occur, teachers require systematic assistance from subject advisors to stay up to date on curriculum changes and best practices (Langelaan, Gaikhorst, Smets & Oostdam, 2024). Teachers might find it difficult to provide the best instruction without this official support, which could eventually affect the learning outcomes of the learners.

Conclusion

Challenges with ATP pacing can lead to stress and burnout among teachers, particularly if they are not provided with adequate guidance and support. When teachers struggle to keep up with the curriculum pace, it can result in rushed or superficial coverage of important topics, which may affect students' understanding and retention of the material. Ensuring that teachers have the necessary resources, time, and support to manage the ATP effectively is decisive for maintaining high-quality instruction (Ball & Cohen, 1999). The DoE should regularly check in with teachers to assess their progress and provide additional support where needed to ensure that the curriculum is being delivered effectively. The issues highlighted in the quote underscore the importance of consistent and ongoing professional development and support for teachers. The infrequency of workshops and the absence of follow-up from the DoE create significant challenges for teachers, who may feel ill-equipped to manage the demands of the curriculum and address the needs of their students. This situation can lead to decreased teaching quality, which ultimately affects student learning outcomes.

To improve the situation, the DoE should consider implementing more frequent workshops and establishing a robust system for follow-up support. This could include regular check-ins with teachers, additional training sessions throughout the year, and creating platforms for teachers to share challenges and solutions with their peers. By providing continuous support, the DoE can help teachers better manage their workload, improve their instructional practices, and enhance student learning.

Recommendations

There is a need for regular and adequate continuous professional development for secondary school teachers to enhance their instructional skills and strategies. This would help teachers improve their abilities and modify their methods to cover more curriculum and provide higher-quality education. It is recommended that professional development sessions last longer than one-day workshops. Teachers should be equipped with thorough knowledge, creative ways to connect theory and practice, and ample time to put what they learn in these workshops into practice. This would enable them to modify and familiarise to the recently acquired knowledge. Instructive coaching programs, in which seasoned teachers mentor new teachers one-on-one to enhance teaching techniques, could be implemented during the summer break. The administration of the school should offer sufficient internal support for grooming teachers on various strategies specifically related on managing time effectively, curriculum coverage, promoting learner engagement and assessing learning.

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Author Information

Gladys Phumzile Mngomezulu

Department of Curriculum and Instructional Studies,
University of Zululand, South Africa

Kofi Nkonkonya Mpuangnan

Department of Curriculum and Instructional Studies,
University of Zululand, South Africa

Samantha Govender

Department of Curriculum and Instructional Studies,
University of Zululand, South Africa
